

The Cube of Classical Electron Diameter is Precisely the Mass of the Observable Universe. All 26 Sporadic Groups Involved. The Volume = Entropy of the Observable Universe (Only Now!). Λ CDM Problems. Black Hole Electron Related to the Mass of the Universe.

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Abstract

The 3rd power (a cube) of a classical electron's diameter ($d = 3.4870 \times 10^{20}$ Planck lengths) is 4.2399×10^{61} Planck lengths³ (Planck volumes). This, if taken in Planck masses (Planck density) is 9.2280×10^{53} kg. According to Planck (2018) the mass of the observable universe is 9.2875×10^{53} kg (estimated range $9.1017 - 9.4732 \times 10^{53}$ kg, dark matter + baryonic matter). The volume of the Hubble sphere ($r = 14.4$ billion ly) is 2.508×10^{183} Planck volumes, a 4.2399×10^{61} Planck volume would fit into it 5.915×10^{121} times. This is very close to the cube root of the order of the direct product of all the 26 sporadic groups: 6.145×10^{121} . The volume of the observable universe is 8.445×10^{184} Planck volumes, this new fundamental volume would fit in 1.992×10^{123} times. The surface area of the observable universe is 9.3053×10^{123} Planck areas and the entropy is $4\times$ smaller – 2.326×10^{123} – that is 4 Planck areas on the particle horizon code for about (or precisely) 1 classical electron volume inside the universe. A black hole the mass of an electron would have a diameter of 2.706×10^{-57} m, a "string of black holes" around the circumference of the observable universe ($r = 46.5$ billion ly) would contain 1.022×10^{83} black hole electrons with weight of 9.31×10^{53} kg, which is inside the mass of the observable universe given by Planck (2018).

The classical electron diameter is defined as a separation length between two elementary charges that will give a potential energy that equals the mass of the carrier of the elementary charge – the electron. This separation leads to a fundamental length of $d = 5.6360 \times 10^{-15}$ m (3.4870×10^{20} Planck lengths), which is the diameter of the classical electron. This leads to a fundamental volume that is the third power of this length in Planck units - 4.2399×10^{61} Planck volumes. This directly translates to a mass of 4.2399×10^{61} Planck masses (via Planck density).

How many fundamental volumes would fit into a Hubble radius? Current Hubble radius is estimated to be 14.4 billion ly (14.12 – 14.68 billion ly). 14.4 billion ly is 2.508×10^{183} Planck volumes, a 4.2399×10^{61} Planck volume would fit into it 5.915×10^{121} times. This is very close to the cube root of the order of the direct product of all the 26 sporadic groups: 6.145×10^{121} . The fit would be precise with $r = 14.58$ billion ly, which is inside the current uncertainty range.

The volume of the observable universe is 8.445×10^{184} Planck volumes, this new fundamental volume would fit in 1.992×10^{123} times. The surface area of the observable universe is 9.3053×10^{123} Planck areas and the entropy is $4\times$ smaller – 2.326×10^{123} (treating the particle horizon as an event horizon of a black hole) – that is 4 Planck areas on the particle horizon code for about (or precisely) 1 classical electron volume inside the universe.

A black hole the mass of electron would have a diameter of 2.706×10^{-57} m, a "string of pearls" around the circumference of the observable universe ($r = 46.5$ billion ly) would contain 1.022×10^{83} black hole electrons, such an object would weight 9.31×10^{53} kg, which is inside the mass of the observable universe given by Planck (2018).

As a side-note (that is likely to be a mere coincidence) the Janko 4 group J4 has order of 86775571046077562880, which if taken in Planck masses would yield a black hole with a diameter of 3.4709×10^{20} Planck lengths. This value is within about 0.5 % of our fundamental length of 3.4870×10^{20} Planck lengths.

More interesting is the case of a black hole electron. A black hole the mass of an electron would have a diameter of 2.706×10^{-57} m. If we try to build a loop around the universe out of these black holes, we'll need 1.022×10^{83} black hole electrons ($r = 46.5$ billion ly). The mass of such a loop would be 9.31×10^{53} kg, which is inside the mass of the observable universe given by Planck (2018). This hints at a relation between the mass of the electron and the observable universe.

The standard model of cosmology – Λ CDM proposes an observable universe that starts with near 0 mass and one that ends with a mass of about 2.3×10^{54} kg (as time approaches infinity) and with a Hubble radius growing from near 0 size to about 18 billion ly in the future (proper distance). This is obviously hard to square with these observations. It would have to be quite a coincidence for the cube of the classical electron diameter to correspond to the mass of the observable universe precisely at this very moment in time. Same goes for the Hubble sphere volume/cube root of sporadic groups relationship – and as presented here: (<https://vixra.org/abs/2210.0003>) – the volume of observable universe/sporadic groups correspondence. The correspondence between the entropy of the universe and the derived volume is yet another time-dependent coincidence. Note that the current universe diameter/Hubble radius ratio in proper distance is quite close to 2π .

It is quite likely that Λ CDM has fatal issues and a new model for the universe, most likely based on the 26 sporadic groups and group theory, will have to be developed.

Conclusion

It has been shown that the diameter of the classical electron is related to the current mass of the observable universe and that the derived volume is related to the direct product of the 26 sporadic groups. It has been shown that this derived volume is related to the entropy of the observable universe. It has been shown that the diameter of a "black hole electron" is related to the current mass of the observable universe.